

Dynamic Analysis of Complex Structures Based on Octree Scaled Boundary Finite Element Method

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ABSTRACT:

The traditional finite element method (FEM) has limitations in the meshing and calculation accuracy of complex models, and additional technology is required to handle the hanging nodes. The article uses the user defined element (UEL) of commercial software ABAQUS to implement a three-dimensional scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM). The proposed algorithm can integrate octree mesh and SBFEM on commercial software ABAQUS-UEL and it can recognize complex STL models. The accuracy of the proposed algorithm is verified by several numerical models. The results show that the proposed algorithm can successfully integrate octree and SBFEM without dealing with hanging nodes. It also reduces the number of model elements, ensures the accuracy of the calculation results and improves the calculation efficiency. Combined with ABAQUS, it can be used for mesh generation and seismic dynamic analysis of complex STL models, which has obvious computational advantages compared with the traditional FEM.

Keywords: scaled boundary finite element method; octree mesh; STL model; UEL; ABAQUS; seismic analysis.

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INTRODUCTION

Nowadays many numerical methods have been applied to structural analysis among which the finite element method (FEM) [1] occupies a dominant position, because of its simple implementation and strong versatility. Finite element analysis initially discretizes the problem geometry into a mesh with simple geometric elements. Commonly used element types in three dimensions include tetrahedral and hexahedral element. In the current development process, tetrahedrons are more mature in technology and have higher geometry adaptive capability but there is an obvious disadvantage of low calculation accuracy. Complex models often require more calculation meshes to meet the calculation and analysis requirements. This will cause the computer to require a large amount, of calculations and analysis for complex models. It takes a lot of time to ensure its convergence. Hexahedral elements have high solution accuracy but compared with tetrahedral elements, they have the disadvantage of poor geometric adaptability [2] .For large and complex structural models, the mesh will be distorted in the larger deformation region.

Using the traditional hexahedral element division to construct a high-fidelity computation model is challenging, particularly for large-scale and complicated models with huge spans, different material properties between dam and foundation. In order to ensure the establishment of high-fidelity model designers often need to simplify areas where the model scale changes greatly in the early stage. The consequence of such processing is that the accuracy of the calculation results cannot be guaranteed which making it difficult to provide guidance for relevant actual projects. For a long time there has not been a good way to deal with the problem of fine modeling of large and complex models which has also become one of the bottlenecks restricting numerical simulation calculations of such problems.

With the proposal of the scaled boundary finite element method (SBFEM) [3, 4] , it has become one of the methods to overcome such problems. As a semi-analytical numerical method, it combines FEM and the boundary element method (BEM). The advantage of [5, 6] is that only discretization is performed on the element surface and analytical solution is performed inside the element which can reduce the dimension of the problem by one dimension and SBFEM does not need to give a fundamental solution of the research domain in advance. The discretization of directions (boundaries) is similar to FEM and has the accuracy of FEM . Over the last thirty years, SBFEM has been applied by scholars to various types of problem analysis, including finite field wave propagation problems [7], fracture mechanics [8,9], contact mechanics [10,11], seepage [12], elastic-plastic damage analysis [13], adaptive analysis [14,15] etc.

Recently, both quadtree and octree composition techniques have been implemented into SBFEM for mesh generation [16-18] .In quadtree meshes, there is no hanging nodes in SBFEM because each quadtree cell can be considered as a subdomain with any number of line elements on the edge. Although hanging nodes are present in the octree mesh. Octree element with hanging nodes can simply be divided into a combination of standard triangle and quadrilateral faces without additional work. This article mainly introduces related octree mesh generation technology while choosing the Standard Tessellation Language (STL) format [21] as the input file format because it is widely supported in CAD industries such as 3D printing and rapid prototyping which only contains unstructured triangular faces used to describe the surface of an object. Furthermore, pathological, overlapping and self-intersecting faces are allowed in this file. These advantages of STL files make the proposed meshing technique versatile and easy to use. Based on the open source UEL program [22] , the octree mesh pre-processing program is compiled to realize the combination of the octree scaled boundary finite element method and ABAQUS finite element software. This article first gives the basic formula of three-dimensional SBFEM, then introduces the mesh division and element generation based on STL file data as well as the octree mesh implementation process and hanging node processing method based on the user subroutine UEL. Finally, through several examples the numerical model verifies the feasibility of this algorithm.

1.THREE-DIMENSIONAL SCALED BOUNDARY FINITE ELEMENT METHOD

In the three-dimensional scale boundary coordinate system (ξ, η, ζ) , ξ it is the radial coordinate, η and ζ are called circumferential coordinates. The scaling center needs to be set in the SBFEM. The scaling center can be set at any position in the subdomain on the premise that all boundaries are visible. At the same time, discretization needs to be performed on the boundary. Each face on the polyhedron must be discretized into triangles and quadrilateral as shown in Figure 1. Any point in the subdomain b, the coordinates (x, y, z) of the Cartesian coordinate system of the point in the local coordinate system express by ξ, η and ζ :

Figure 1. A Sketch of the Subdomain of SBFEM

$$x(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = x_0 + \xi ([N(\eta, \zeta)] \{x\} - x_0) \quad (1)$$

$$y(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = y_0 + \xi ([N(\eta, \zeta)] \{y\} - y_0) \quad (2)$$

$$z(\xi, \eta, \zeta) = z_0 + \xi ([N(\eta, \zeta)] \{z\} - z_0) \quad (3)$$

Using the same shape function to interpolate the geometry and displacement fields piecewise, we have:

$$\{u\} = [N_u] \{u(\xi)\} \quad (4)$$

The strain is expressed as:

$$\{\varepsilon(\xi, \eta, \zeta)\} = \left([B_1] \{u_{,\xi}\} + \frac{1}{\xi} [B_2] \{u_{,\xi}\} \right) \quad (5)$$

According to the relationship between stress and strain in elastic mechanics, the expression is as follows:

$$\{\sigma(\xi, \eta, \zeta)\} = [D]\{\varepsilon(\xi, \eta, \zeta)\} = [D]\left([B_1]\{u_{,\xi}\} + \frac{1}{\xi}[B_2]\{u_{,\xi}\}\right) \quad (6)$$

When the physical force including the external load and initial stress acting in the s domain is 0, the three-dimensional static balance equation is:

$$[E_0]\xi^2\{u(\xi)\}_{,\xi\xi} + (2[E_0] - [E_1] + [E_1]^T)\xi\{u(\xi)\}_{,\xi} + ([E_1]^T - [E_2])\{u(\xi)\} = 0 \quad (7)$$

This formula is the Euler-Cauchy differential equation. In order to solve the second-order differential equation, a variable is introduced and converted into a first-order ordinary differential equation. The expression of this variable is:

$$X(\xi) = \begin{cases} \xi^{0.5}u(\xi) \\ \xi^{-0.5}q(\xi) \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Convert the second-order differential equation into a first-order differential equation:

$$\xi X(\xi)_{,\xi} = -ZX(\xi) \quad (9)$$

Finally, the radial displacement interpolation function and internal node force vector are obtained:

$$u(\xi) = \Psi_u \xi^{-S_n - 0.5} \Psi_u^{-1} u_b \quad (10)$$

$$q(\xi) = \Psi_q \xi^{-S_n - 0.5} \Psi_q^{-1} u_b \quad (11)$$

Where, Ψ_u, Ψ_q are the displacement mode and stress mode corresponding to the eigenvalue, respectively, and their dimensions are equal to the number of degrees of freedom of the boundary surface element.

2. MESH SEPARATION AND ELEMENT GENERATION BASED ON STL FILE DATA

2.1 Introduction to STL File Data

Cloud data obtained by scanning and uses a large number of triangular facets to approximate the surface of the entity. There will be a large amount of point cloud data in the area where the entity has large curvature and singular points and there will also be relatively dense triangular facets. This sparse-dense transition method optimizes the entity approximation effect. The recorded unstructured triangular mesh information consists of the surface normal vector of the triangular facet, the vertices arranged according to the right-hand spiral rule and the Cartesian coordinate system. Figure 2 is a schematic diagram of the topological information of the STL file of a simple tetrahedron with only the external normal vectors of two faces marked. For the triangular face adc, the arrangement order of

the three nodes and the external normal vector n_1 follow the right-hand rule and the representation of the remaining three facets follows the same rule.

Figure 2. Schematic Diagram of Topological Information of Tetrahedron in STL file

2.2 Construction of STL File Based on Hierarchical Data Structure Topology Information

The STL file internally uses the surface as the basic data element to store information. Each data element records the outer normal vector and node coordinate information of the surface. Since the information of each triangular patch is all concentrated in the data element, this requires the establishment of a hierarchical data to connect the three types of data of nodes, edges and triangular patches.

This hierarchical data structure is divided into three levels: node data set, edge data set and triangle patch data set. The node data set stores node numbers and corresponding node coordinates. In addition to the node coordinates of the model, the three components of the outer normal vector are also stored in the data set in the form of node coordinates. The edge data set stores the edge data after the triangular patch is split including the two node numbers of the edge. The order of the node numbers here cannot be reversed and needs to be stored in the order before splitting from the triangular patch. The triangle patch data set stores the numbers of the three edges of each face and the outer normal vector. The data form of the outer normal vector has a certain similarity with the node coordinates, so it is numbered in the form of nodes. This hierarchical data structure is interoperable and the levels can be accessed through the intermediate level which greatly reduces the data search time of the program.

2.3 Cell Topology Information Generation

In SBFEM, numerical integration is performed based on the element surface. It is not possible to extract all of the element's surface-node information in the octree mesh solution by depending only on the element node arrangement order without referring to the geometric diagram of the element. In the process of SBFEM algorithm programming, additional information is needed to describe the topological information of the SBFEM element. In order to accurately describe the element topological information based on SBFEM, four types of data information are added on the basis of the element node information of the classical finite element, namely: node coordinate information, surface information, element information and scale center information.

The node coordinate information is the coordinate information of all nodes in the model. Each row of the data consists of four columns. The first column is the node number of the node and the next three columns are the x, y, and z coordinate values. Surface information refers to splitting all elements of the model and all surfaces are combined together to form the data. The surface shared by the element only appears once in the surface information and the number of rows and columns in the surface information is different. The value in the first column is the number of nodes of the surface followed by the node number information of the surface. These node numbers are connected in sequence to form a closed face. The number in the first column of each row of element information is the number of faces of the element followed by the signed face numbers. Each number represents the corresponding face in the face information. The node order and scaling center of the face satisfy the right-hand rule then the sign is negative otherwise it is positive. The scaling center information is the scale center of all elements in the model. This data information is formally the same as the node coordinate information.

Figure a show the model diagram composed of standard octree meshes and Figure b is the supplementary element topology information of Figure 3. If only rely on ordinary model information, it is impossible to extract the node information of all faces of the octree mesh. After adding additional topology information, all face node information can be easily obtained through indexing.

Figure 3. Example of an Octree Element and Supplementary Topology Information

3. IMPLEMENTATION OF UEL OCTREE MESH

3.1 Separation of Octree Mesh Planes

Octree meshes can be created by discretizing the boundaries into surface elements, while the volume of the domain itself is not discretized. This paper takes the cube element as a typical example of using SBFEM octree mesh as shown in Figure a. Due to the additional higher-order terms in the approximation space, quadrilateral elements usually perform better than triangular elements. Therefore, a method is proposed to generate the octree mesh surface into three-node and four-node surfaces without adding additional nodes. In order to be compatible with ABAQUS, the element library remains consistent and the processing of hanging nodes is shown in Figure b and Figure c.

Figure 4. Present a Cube Element Octree Mesh along with the Five-Node and Six-Node Generation Processes of the Octree Mesh

3.2 UEL Workflow Based on ABAQUS User Subroutine

ABAQUS is a powerful software. Using the user-defined element subroutine interface provided by ABAQUS which can combine the flexibility of SBFEM meshing with the powerful linear solver and pre/post-processing module of ABAQUS for complex models. Compared with the traditional FEM, static and linear elastic dynamic analysis has the advantages of shorter time and higher accuracy [22].

ABAQUS are provided by the user subroutine UEL. Through the superposition of standard finite elements with negligible stiffness and polyhedral user elements provided in the ABAQUS element library, the element surface is created on the polyhedral user element and the interaction is established. Throughout the standard ABAQUS analysis, UEL is used to read the pre-computed stiffness and mass matrices and is directly used to define the required output arrays AMATRIX and RHS. Finally, the convergence of the solution is checked by calling UEL. The specific process is as shown in the figure 5.

Figure 5. UEL Workflow Diagram

The open-source UEL [20] implements linear elastic polyhedral elements into ABAQUS. In order to be consistent with the element library of ABAQUS, the surfaces of the polyhedral elements are only discretized into triangles and quadrilaterals to perform Gaussian integral. The distribution of Gaussian integration points on three-node and four-node surfaces is shown in Tables 1 and 2:

Table 1. Three-Node Surface Gaussian Integration Point Distribution

Points	ξ Coordinate	η Coordinate	ω Point weight
	$\xi_1 = 1/6$	$\eta_1 = \xi_1$	$\omega_1 = 1/3$
	$\xi_2 = 2/3$	$\eta_2 = \xi_1$	$\omega_2 = 1/3$
	$\xi_3 = 1/6$	$\eta_3 = \xi_2$	$\omega_3 = 1/3$

Table 2. Four-Node Surface Gaussian Integration Point Distribution

Points	ξ Coordinate	η Coordinate	ω Point weight
	$\xi_1 = -1/\sqrt{3}$	$\eta_1 = \xi_1$	$\omega_1 = 1/4$
	$\xi_2 = 1/\sqrt{3}$	$\eta_2 = \xi_1$	$\omega_2 = 1/4$
	$\xi_3 = 1/\sqrt{3}$	$\eta_3 = \xi_2$	$\omega_3 = 1/4$
	$\xi_4 = -1/\sqrt{3}$	$\eta_4 = \xi_2$	$\omega_4 = 1/4$

4. VERIFICATION OF EXAMPLE

4.1 Dynamic Characteristics Analysis of an Iron Tower Model

In order to study the application of complex STL models in actual practice, this article selects an iron tower as a prototype then establishes an STL model with simplified details and analyzes the natural vibration frequency of its structure. The calculated STL tower model [24] has a size of 41.38m × 41.38m × 92.22m and a fixed boundary is imposed on the bottom to constrain its rigid body displacement in three directions. This calculation example is only for checking the calculation accuracy of the relevant model. The material parameters of Q235 steel are used for calculation as a whole. The elastic modulus $E = 1.8 \times 10^{11}$ Pa, Poisson's ratio $\mu = 0.3$, and density $\rho = 7800$ kg/m³.

The results of calculation using different mesh types using the SBFEM are compared with the results of traditional FEM. Table 3 shows the mesh information of three different calculation schemes. The three-dimensional overall and partial model diagrams of the model are shown in Figure 9. The overall and partial model mesh sections or front views of the three working conditions are shown in Figures 10-12. For condition 1 (SBFEM + octree mesh), while reducing the degree of freedom of the model, the mesh is refined at the corresponding transformation point of the tower model. It can be seen that while comparing calculation condition 1 with calculation conditions 2 and 3, the number of elements in condition 1 is reduced by nearly 40,000. The first 100 orders of the three working condition calculation models are extracted for comparative analysis. Figure 6 is a comparison chart of the three results. It can be seen from the results that the octree mesh can be used to reduce the number of model elements while ensuring the accuracy of the calculation results. Simultaneously, combining the SBFEM does not require additional technology to handle suspension nodes, which has significant computational advantages compared to traditional FEM.

Table 3. Model Information

	Condition 1	Condition 2	Condition 3
	SBFEM(octree mesh)	SBFEM(tetrahedral mesh)	FEM(tetrahedral mesh)
Number of elements	68684	102721	167393
Number of faces	195140	223033	502179
Number of nodes	96763	25541	260007

Figure 6. STL 3D Overall and Local Model of the Tower & Overall and Partial Model Mesh Profiles for Case 1

Figure 7. Overall and Partial Model Mesh Profiles for Case 2 & Front View of the Overall and Local Model Mesh of Case 3

Figure 8. The First 100 Natural Frequencies of the Model

4.2 Dynamic Time History Analysis of a Certain High Arch Dam

4.2.1 Project Introduction

A high arch dam in southwest of China is selected as the research object. This project is located at the junction of Yanyuan County and Muli County, Liangshan Prefecture, Sichuan Province, China. It's on the main stream of the Yalong River Bend. It is a concrete double-curved arch dam. The crest elevation of the arch dam is 1885 m and the maximum dam height is 305 m. The thickness of the arch crown beam top and arch crown beam bottom of the arch dam are 16 m and 63 m respectively. The normal water storage level of the reservoir is 1880 m. In front of the dam, The, silt elevation is 1644.10 m, the silt floating bulk density is 500 kg/m³ and the earthquake fortification intensity is 0.269g.

4.2.2 Analysis of Calculation Conditions

The mesh at the input boundary and the contact boundary at the dam foundation interface were refined in order to simulate the influence of seismic motion on the dam in more detail. The corresponding results are compared with the finite element results. To compare the differences between the FEM and the user subroutine UEL developed in this article based on ABAQUS where two distinct mesh generation types are explicitly chosen. Table 4 displays information of several model elements. The mesh diagrams for specific working conditions are shown in Figures 9 to 10:

Working condition one: FEM is used to model by ABAQUS, and the element type is C3D8.

Working condition two: The ABAQUS UEL is used in combination with the SBFEM for calculation. The element generation type is octree mesh.

Figure 9. 3D Model of High Arch Dam & Mesh of Condition 1

Figure 10. Mesh for condition 2 & Mesh Profile of Condition 3

Table 4. Different Model Element Information

	Element information	Node information	Degrees of freedom information
Working condition one	56306	61940	185820
Working condition two	15188	22857	68571

4.2.3 Material Parameters and Ground Motion Input

The interaction between the soil and the structure should be considered in the seismic analysis of dam. This paper uses a simple massless foundation model to consider the flexibility of the soil. The concrete and foundation materials are linear elastic. The specific material parameters are shown in Table 5:

Table 5. Material Parameters of Dam Body and Foundation

	Dam	Foundation
Modulus of elasticity (GPa)	28.8	30
Poisson's ratio	0.167	0.2
Density (kg/m ³)	2400	0

The maximum accelerations of ground motion applied in the horizontal and vertical directions are 0.49g and 0.34g respectively. The seismic wave acceleration record is shown in Figure 18. This ground motion is input in the form of node amplitude on the base and side of the dam. The 10 seconds of the ground motion are taken for calculation and the calculation step is 0.01s.

Figure 11. Seismic Time History Curve

4.2.4 Analysis of Earthquake Dynamic Response Results

The same computer (processor: 13th Gen Intel(R) Core (TM) i5-13400 2.50 GHz) is used to calculate both working conditions. The acceleration, velocity and displacement of the dam crest and dam heel points under two different working conditions are extracted. Relevant data, comparative analysis of the horizontal relative acceleration, relative velocity and relative displacement time history of the dam top and dam heel points is shown in Figures 12.

Figure 12. Show the Relative Displacements between the Dam Crest and Heel in the Cross-River Direction, along the River, and in the Vertical Direction

The results indicate that working condition one is 3.7 times more numerous than working condition two. The maximum relative displacement difference between the dam crest and the dam heel point in the transverse direction is 1.3%, the maximum relative displacement difference in the longitudinal direction is 3.1%, and the maximum vertical relative displacement difference is 5.1%. In summary, based on the assumption of accuracy, working condition two's calculation efficiency is significantly better than working condition one's.

CONCLUSION

The proposed algorithm in this article can recognize STL file data information, and integrate octree mesh and SBFEM in commercial software. It does not require additional techniques to deal with hanging nodes. This program is used to conduct dynamic analysis of a specific high arch dam and an iron tower STL model. The results show that the use of octree mesh can reduce the number of elements to improve calculation efficiency while ensuring calculation accuracy by providing a new method for dynamic analysis of complex structures.

REFERENCES

- [1] O. C. Zienkiewicz, R. L. Taylor, and J. Z. Zhu, *The Finite Element Method: Its Basis and Fundamentals*, 6th ed. Amsterdam, The Netherlands: Elsevier Butterworth-Heinemann, 2005.
- [2] C. R. Dohrmann, M. W. Heinstein, and J. Jung, "Node-based uniform strain elements for three-node triangular and four-node tetrahedral meshes," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 47, no. 9, pp. 1549–1568, 2000, doi: 10.1002/(SICI)1097-0207(20000330)47:9<1549::AID-NME842>3.0.CO;2-K.
- [3] J. P. Wolf and C. Song, "The scaled boundary finite-element method — a primer: derivations," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 78, no. 1–3, pp. 191–210, 2000.
- [4] C. Song and J. P. Wolf, "The scaled boundary finite-element method — a primer: solution procedures," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 78, no. 1–3, pp. 211–225, 2000.
- [5] P. K. Banerjee and R. Butterfield, *Boundary Element Methods in Engineering Science*. (Publication details not available; classical reference text; no DOI found).

- [6] A. H. D. Cheng and D. T. Cheng, "Heritage and early history of the boundary element method," *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 268–302, 2005.
- [7] M. Bazyar and C. Song, "A continued-fraction-based high-order transmitting boundary for wave propagation in unbounded domains of arbitrary geometry," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 74, no. 2, pp. 209–237, 2008.
- [8] C. Song, E. Ooi, and S. Natarajan, "A review of the scaled boundary finite element method for two-dimensional linear elastic fracture mechanics," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 187, pp. 45–73, 2018.
- [9] K. Coelho, P. Devloo, and S. Gomes, "Error estimates for the scaled boundary finite element method," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 379, p. 113765, 2020.
- [10] W. Xing, C. Song, and F. Tin-Loi, "A scaled boundary finite element-based node-to-node scheme for 2D frictional contact problems," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 333, pp. 114–146, 2018.
- [11] W. Xing, J. Zhang, C. Song, et al., "A node-to-node scheme for three-dimensional contact problems using the scaled boundary finite element method," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 347, pp. 928–956, 2019.
- [12] J. Liu, J. Li, L. Peng, et al., "New application of the isogeometric boundary representations methodology with SBFEM to seepage problems in complex domains," *Computers and Fluids*, vol. 174, pp. 241–255, 2018.
- [13] Z. Zhang, D. Disssnsyake, A. Saputra, et al., "Three-dimensional damage analysis by the scaled boundary finite element method," *Computers & Structures*, vol. 206, pp. 1–17, 2018.
- [14] Hirshikesh, A. Pramod, R. Annabattula, et al., "Adaptive phase-field modeling of brittle fracture using the scaled boundary finite element method," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 355, pp. 284–307, 2019.
- [15] J. Zhang, S. Natarajan, E. Ooi, et al., "Adaptive analysis using scaled boundary finite element method in 3D," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 372, p. 113374, 2020.
- [16] E. T. Ooi, H. Man, S. Natarajan, et al., "Adaptation of quadtree meshes in the scaled boundary finite element method for crack propagation modelling," *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, vol. 144, pp. 101–117, 2015.
- [17] A. Saputra, H. Talebi, D. Tran, et al., "Automatic image-based stress analysis by the scaled boundary finite element method," *International Journal for Numerical Methods in Engineering*, vol. 109, no. 5, pp. 697–738, 2017.
- [18] D. Zou, K. Chen, X. Kong, et al., "An enhanced octree polyhedral scaled boundary finite element method and its applications in structure analysis," *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements*, vol. 84, pp. 87–107, 2017.
- [19] Y. Liu, A. A. Saputra, J. Wang, et al., "Automatic polyhedral mesh generation and scaled boundary finite element analysis of STL models," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 313, pp. 106–132, 2017.
- [20] S. Ya, S. Eisenträger, C. Song, et al., "An open-source ABAQUS implementation of the scaled boundary finite element method to study interfacial problems using polyhedral meshes," *Computer Methods in Applied Mechanics and Engineering*, vol. 381, p. 113766, 2021.
- [21] Z. J. Yang, F. Yao, and Y. J. Huang, "Development of ABAQUS UEL/VUEL subroutines for scaled boundary finite element method for general static and dynamic stress analyses," *Engineering Analysis with Boundary Elements*, vol. 114, pp. 58–73, 2020.
- [22] Thingiverse.com. Thingiverse | 3D Printing Models & Designs Platform. [Online]. Available: <https://www.thingiverse.com>

